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Research Article

**INVESTIGATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING PROMOTE
STRATEGIC THINKING ON PUBLIC MANAGERS IN IRAN****Mohammad Ali Manafzadeh¹, Parya Amirhasani², Sherareh Mefahkeri³, Samira Taheri⁴,
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Branch, Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj, Iran;**Abstract:**

The purpose of this research, investigate the factors influencing promote strategic thinking in government executives been. This research as the objective, functional and is terms from a variety of descriptive research method and the method of data collection is the survey type. Accordingly to assess the basic concepts research in order borrowed from questionnaire Joon Moon (2013) to assess effective factors that includes seven variable been And to assess strategic thinking is questionnaire Liedtka (1998) been used. The population consisted of 27 senior and middle managers of the Company Sanandaj city been. Reliability of the questionnaire Cronbach's alpha for two variables referred, respectively, 0/809 and 0/831 calculated. The final findings of research suggests a relationship between the factors (tendency managers on risk taking, reward system, amount official, centralized, intersectional collaboration, technology capability, creativity) with strategic thinking in Company Sanandaj city been.

Keywords: Strategic Thinking, Administrators Governmental, Public Managers, Iran**Corresponding author:****Soran Mowlaie,**

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INTRODUCTION:

For at least the past 30 years, the literature has admonished organizational leaders and managers for their lack of strategic thinking and urged its development to improve organization performance [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Seek to design new threats, Mintzberg (the distinction between analytic and synthetic processes that negate the subjective followed by strategic planning), and Hamel & Parahald (strategic organization rather than strategic planning and others), strategic thinking as a modern approach in planning and management was strategic [6]. Due to the lack of clear meaning of the word a lot of strategic thinking and considerable confusion in management are observed [7]. Wilson [8] Argues that strategic thinking is just thinking about strategic issues and because changes in the characteristics of strategic plans and its evolution, today is better than it is named as thinking and strategic management. Stacey [9] Strategic thinking, deductive and quantitative use of similes to engage new creative ideas and design new learning considers consistent. "Strategic thinking" is important for strategy development and strategic management [10, 11, 12, 4, 2, 13, 14, 15], and contributes to corporate outputs, and profitability [16].

Strategic thinking has been researched in both the management and psychological literature with the management literature focusing on the process of strategic thinking and making strategic decisions [12, 17] whereas the psychological literature has focused on factors affecting strategic thinking and decision making [18, 19]. This review provides an overview of both the approaches and identifies the importance of considering both the approaches together so that an understanding of what makes a good strategic decision maker can be sought.

Strategic thinking is an approach based on the principles of strategy, divergent and creative thinking to create value creator recommends a strategy. More strategic thinking and methodological aspects of the process sees the strategy as an art [20]. Basis for strategic planning, forecasting environment (opportunities and threats) is the future and where the forecast (in the plan) and reality (at runtime) there are many differences, its effectiveness will disappear [21]. In such circumstances, strategic thinking, especially when this type of thinking is distributed among middle managers throughout the organization to improve efficiency and effectiveness of the organization [22].

Ken Ohmae, In his authoritative book " Thinking a strategist" suggests that if basic issues do not

recognize, no matter how your employees to enter and physical stress ultimately result can not be achieved except confusion and defeat. Finally, we can say that strategic thinking in all companies, public commitment creates. The purpose of this thinking, is not predicting the future but the early detection of market changes and see opportunities that others do not see it. What is clear strategic thinking on the company's vision and strategy of the company in the direction it moves [23]. The common characteristics of strategic thinking mentioned by a number of literatures are: visionary, creative, and synthetic. Other characteristics mentioned by some literature are analytical, conceptual, divergent, and systematic. Generally, strategic thinking, insight and understanding of the situation and take advantage of opportunities. This insight helps to correct and timely market realities and rules to be known and to meet these conditions create new solutions and value creation [24]. Strategic thinking is a vital skill in the management of the new millennium. Empowerment requires the skill to survive and grow in today's highly competitive environment [25]. Strategic Thinking art architecture is a strategy based on creativity, discover and understand the business discontinuities [26]. Strategic thinking is planning new measures based learning [9]. Rowe et al. [27] define strategic thinking as a process of thinking about an organization and how to go about developing a strategy which includes vision, creativity, flexibility, and entrepreneurship. Graetz [28] suggests the role of strategic thinking as "seeking innovation and imagining new and very different futures that may lead a company to redefine its core strategies and its industry." Graetz [15] combines the attributes of strategic thinking suggested by Mintzberg [12] and Heracleous [29] and added innovative thinking. Bonn [14] proposes "strategic thinking" as a core competency of an organization. Bonn [1] defines "strategic thinking" as a way to solve strategic problems, combining a rational and convergent strategic approach with a creative and convergent thought process and proposes a conceptual framework of strategic thinking which consists of system thinking, creativity, and vision.

In the search for the definition of strategic thinking, there are at present a variety of approaches. Although the concept of strategic thinking has been in the literature for over a quarter of a century, the term is often used interchangeably with other aspects related to the development of organizational direction, such as "strategy", "strategic management" and "strategic planning" [14, 2]. Creativity and innovations seems to happen and disappear and in rare cases, their high level can be maintained for a longer period while

operating effectively and efficiently. The strategic level of decision making is based less on the rational and more in the spiritual source of vision and therefore it is extremely hard to accomplish in a methodical way. Strategic thinking has also been defined as a method of gathering competitive intelligence or information that may have strategic value [31]. Zabriskie and Huellmantel [11] defined it as the prelude for designing an organization's future. When discussing about strategic thinking, definitions are not precise and therefore they just comment one part of the completely big strategic thinking picture.

Mintzberg [12] introduced a concept of strategic thinking as "seeing": seeing ahead and behind, seeing above and below, seeing beside and beyond, and seeing it through. Boar [31] points out that strategists think about multiple issues concurrently and that synthesis lies at the heart of strategic thinking. Saloner et al. [13] depict "strategic thinking" as the ability to develop and maintain conceptual maps of a business, and the ability to tie together changes initiated outside the firm's context, actions, and

performance. Strategic thinking first requires the conceptualization of a new strategy and later thinking through how changes in the external and internal environment will impact the strategy, they added. To assess the level of strategic thinking and strategic thinking in the organization must first identify and then measured them in our organization [32]. Among the strategic thinking patterns, the five elements of strategic thinking Jane Liedtka widely accepted and used [20]. Liedtka model in most research in the field of strategic thinking is discussed and numerous references to his articles in Scopus, bibliographic databases, indicate the widespread use of this model [32]. Ghorbani & Kiani [33] In his article, we review the definitions and models to assess strategic thinking conclude strategic thinking based on Liedtka model over other models compatible with the current state of Iran. Strategic thinking is vital to the sustainability of an organization and often contributes to the redevelopment or tweaking of an organization's mission statement, goals, objectives, and strategies [34].

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model Research

Following Hypothesis present on model:

H₁: There is a relationship between risk orientation and strategic thinking among public managers
H₂: There is a relationship between compensation system and strategic thinking among public managers
H₃: There is a relationship between formality and strategic thinking among public managers

H₄: There is a relationship between centralization and strategic thinking among public managers

H₅: There is a relationship between Units Corporation and strategic thinking among public managers

H₆: There is a relationship between technology ability and strategic thinking among public managers

H₇: There is a relationship between creativity and strategic thinking among public managers

METHODOLOGY:

This research is applicable in terms of goal and descriptive from solidarity category in terms of methodology and is survey in terms of collecting data. Statistical population is public managers that equals to 27 persons

RESULTS:

Due to research method and data collection, in this paper 2 questionnaire consist of factor effecting strategic thinking (19 items) and strategic thinking scales (25 items) used as main data measurements.

Cornbrash's alpha coefficient was used to calculating reliability that the results showed good reliability include 0.85, 0.809 and 0.838 for factor effecting strategic thinking, and strategic thinking respectively.

Table 1: Frequency and percent distribution of respondents

	Scale	Frequency	Percent
Sex	male	23	85/5
	female	4	14/8
	total	27	100
Age	25-35	3	11/1
	36-45	16	59/3
	46-55	7	25/9
	more than 55	1	3/7
	total	27	100
Education	assistance	3	11/1
	bachelor	22	81/5
	master	1	3/7
	phd	1	3/7
	total	27	100
Career	less than 5	1	3/7
	5-10	1	3/7
	10-15	11	40/7
	15-20	3	11/1
	more than 20	11	40/7
	total	27	100

Non parametric spearman test used for measuring relationship between research indexes because data are less than 30 (27).

Hypothesis results are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Spearman test results

	strategic thinking	rejected/confirmed
Risk Orientation	0/834	confirmed
Compensation System	0/701	confirmed
Formality	0/869	confirmed
Centralization	0/773	confirmed
Units Corporation	0/858	confirmed
Technology Ability	0/843	confirmed
Creativity	0/885	confirmed

FINDINGS:

Results of first hypothesis show that there is a relationship between risk orientation and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive.

Results of 2st hypothesis show that there is a relationship between compensation system and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive so this hypothesis

confirmed. Existence of appropriate rules to service recovery based on long term performance and a compensation system based on performance quality has a positive effect on improving strategic thinking among public managers.

Results of 3st hypothesis show that there is a relationship between formality and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive so this hypothesis confirmed. more

respect to rules in company results in more strategic thinking among public managers.

Results of 4st hypothesis show that there is a relationship between centralization and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive so this hypothesis confirmed. When there is a fit relationship between units of company, collective decisions results in strategic thinking among public managers

Results of 5st hypothesis show that there is a relationship between Units Corporation and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive so this hypothesis confirmed. If relationship between employees explicated finely then strategic thinking among public managers improved

Results of 6st hypothesis show that there is a relationship between technology ability and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive so this hypothesis confirmed. Specification of adequate recourses for R&D unit, have a high engineering ability compare to competitors has a positive effect on strategic thinking among public managers

Results of 7st hypothesis show that there is a relationship between creativity and strategic thinking among public managers and this relationship is strait and positive so this hypothesis confirmed. Decision making based on systematic and regular and creative manner, customer orientation, pay attention to organizational value has a positive effect on strategic thinking among public managers.

Suggestions:

- Assign authority to bottom managers
- Settle performance assessing system to bottom managers
- Settle compensation and punishment regime, codification short and long time programs and company view
- Periodic assessing of programs achievement and a full report of failing or succeeding achieves
- Assign current rescotes based on programs

Strategic thinking ability is intrinsic to the mastery of strategic leadership. Strategic leadership requires capability in strategic planning and strategic thinking. Substantial and rapid changes of trends and events in politics, economy and technology in the industrial era have serious effects on the performance and behavior of firms. Research has shown that only a small number of managers, especially third world countries, failed to properly and timely respond to such changes have been and have been able to structure and internal lining to fit the required empowerment in the face of challenges and change

their organization. To coordinate with continuous changes and steps companies need to change the procedure of thought and tolerance towards the objectives of corporate executives is subjective and when faced with new problems, old solutions lose their effectiveness. However, as yet, there is no agreement on what these competencies might represent. Future research should focus on the identification and validation of strategic decision making competencies as well as developing a tool that assesses these competencies and interventions to address weak areas. This will allow organizations to develop/employ the best strategists into their organizations to ensure it maintains a competitive edge.

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